

Report of a Round Table Discussion

Towards Climate- Resilient Adaptation

A dialogue on Heat, Gender
and Maternal Health in Bilaspur,
Chhattisgarh

Contents

■	Acknowledgement	3
■	Preface	5
■	Glossary	6
■	Abbreviations	6
■	Executive Summary	7
■	Section 1: Introduction	8
■	Section 2: Locating The Poor in Bilaspur City	9
■	Section 3: Institutional Support: Government Schemes and Policies for Urban Poor in Bilaspur	11
■	Section 4: Women's Health and Disproportionate Impact of Heat Stress	15
■	Section 5: In Sum: Gendered Determinants of Heat-Health Vulnerabilities	19
■	Section 6: Harnessing Barriers as Points of Leverage for Enabling Change	20
■	Section 7: Recommendations	21

Acknowledgement

The Heat in Pregnancy – India (HiP-I) project team extends its sincere gratitude to all participants who contributed their time, expertise, and insights to the roundtable discussion titled “Extreme Heat, Gender and Maternal Health: A Dialogue Towards Climate-Resilient Adaptation,” held on June 24, 2025. This roundtable was organized under Work Package 3 (WP3) of the HiP-I project. The HiP-I project is funded by the Wellcome Trust and implemented by a consortium of academic and clinical partners, including The George Institute for Global Health India; the Translational Health Science and Technology Institute (THSTI); Gurugram Civil Hospital; Chhattisgarh Institute of Medical Sciences; Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences; Imperial College London;

The University of Oxford; and City St George’s, University of London. The overall Principal Investigator is Prof. (Dr.) Nitya Wadhwa, with project coordination led by Prof. (Dr.) Jane Hirst (UK) and Prof. (Dr.) Shinjini Bhatnagar (India). We acknowledge the valuable contributions of all participants, whose diverse perspectives and multidisciplinary expertise encompassing public health, women’s health, law, veterinary science, education, tribal health, social sciences, urban health, water resources, health and livelihoods, urban planning, and food & nutrition practices enriched the dialogue and outcomes of the roundtable. We are particularly grateful to the distinguished panel of experts who shared their knowledge and experience (listed in alphabetical order).

Names	Expertise	Affiliation and organisation
Ajay Anant	Veterinary health	Outreach worker at Guru Ghasidas Sevardar Sangh, Lok Samata Shikshan Samiti, and Lok Sirjanhaar Union
Devjit Nandi	Water resources	Founder, Navrachna
Dipti Ranjan	Livelihood and food & nutrition practices	Marketing manager, PRADAN
Gayatri Suman	Legal rights	Advocate, Kanooni Margh Darshan Kendra (Nyayika)
Lakan Subodh	Migration and people’s rights	C-Step
Naseem Shriwas	Poverty alleviation	Senior Community Worker, Samarpit
Prafull Chandel	Health and livelihood	Senior Community outreach worker, Jan Swasthya Sahyog
Pratibha J Mishra	Women’s health and livelihood	Professor, Department of Social Work, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya
Priti Rout	Legal expert	Advocate, Independent Practitioner
Sangeeta Sahu	Community engagement	Independent Researcher
Santoshi Varma	Education and health	Founder, Mitwa Mahila Kalyan Seva Samiti
Santoshi Vishwakarma	Women’s health	Nurse at State Mental Health Hospital and Former Outreach Worker Jan Swasthya Sahyog
Satyabhama Awasthi	Urban planning and urban health	Founder, Vasudha Mahila Manch
Shraddha Suman	Lived experiences of a seven-month pregnant woman	Also, a Community Outreach Worker at Jan Sahas

AUTHORS AND CONTRIBUTORS:

Report author: Diana Thomas
 Editing: Dr Chris Mary Kurian
 Conceptualization: Dr Yogesh Jain and Dr Chris Mary Kurian
 Organisation: Dr Yogesh Jain, Dr Chris Mary Kurian, and Diana Thomas,

Project Support: Dr Sangeet Raman Jogi, Dr Yogesh Jain, Dr Praveen Devarsetty, Dr Chris Mary Kurian, Diana Thomas, Sudhakar Reddy Bulla, and Dr Karthika Kumar.

Project Field Team: Bheslal Yadav, Shubham Kumar Mishra, Amit Kumar, Amar Jyoti Tirkey, and Shraddha Pal

HIP- I CONSORTIUM SUPPORT AND FACILITATION

We acknowledge the indispensable contributions of the consortium members, whose behind-the-scenes support, technical expertise, and institutional facilitation made this roundtable possible. Although they did not serve as panellists, their commitment to maternal health research in the context of climate change played a key role in making this critical dialogue possible.

Preface

This report provides insight into the lived experiences of urban poor women in Bilaspur city, with a particular focus on their interactions with extreme heat during pregnancy. The report emerges from a round table discussion held with diverse stakeholders, including civil society representatives working across various domains, researchers, scholars, and a pregnant woman associated with a community-based organisation who generously shared her personal experience. The round table intentionally brought together a majority of women participants in order to centre intersectional feminist perspectives throughout the discussion. This approach ensured that considerations of class and gender shaped both the framing of issues and the understanding of lived experiences shared during the session.

For the participants of the round table, the experiences of poverty, suffering, and ill health were viewed as outcomes of larger systemic issues rather than isolated events. They collectively recognised that social, economic, and health system factors intersect in ways that perpetuate gendered vulnerability and poor maternal health outcomes. Extreme heat, which is part of the broader climate change discourse, was identified as one element of this systemic landscape. Although it was not perceived as the only challenge, many acknowledged that its impacts were not fully understood.

Most roundtable participants lived in and around the neighbourhoods where women reside, and their firsthand experiences of inadequate water supply, recurring electricity shortages during summer, and other everyday hardships strengthened the recognition that this issue requires urgent attention. As a result, the report focuses on unravelling the cyclic interactions of poverty, gender, heat, and health. The purpose of this report is to illuminate the interactions between socioeconomic conditions, climate change, and health consequences, and to offer a contextual understanding and inform the course of our study (Heat in Pregnancy-India). It brings together the complex experiences of Bilaspur's residents, particularly pregnant women, and presents the recommendations developed during the round table to help reduce the adverse impacts of extreme heat on maternal health.

I extend my gratitude to all the participants of the round table for their valuable guidance, insights, and support throughout the preparation of this report.

I hope this report will be useful to readers and will meaningfully contribute to an understanding of the experiences of people, especially pregnant women, who live in informal settlements and who face extreme heat along with other systemic barriers in a rapidly expanding city like Bilaspur, a setting that remains understudied.

Glossary

Kaccha House

Refers to a temporary or semipermanent type of housing or construction made using materials such as mud, thatch, bamboo, or other natural or less durable materials.

Pakka house

Denotes a permanent type of house or construction built with materials such as brick, cement, concrete, or stone, that indicate long-term structural stability.

eShram Cards

Government-issued identification cards under the eShram Portal, created to register unorganized sector workers. The card provides a unique 12-digit Universal Account Number (UAN) enabling access to social security benefits and welfare schemes.

Seva Kendras

Public service centres established to deliver various government services to citizens, including registration, documentation, and benefit applications to avail government schemes. They act as facilitation points for digital and administrative services.

Aadhar Card

A unique identification document issued by the Government of India containing a 12-digit Aadhaar number linked to biometric and demographic data. It serves as proof of identity and address for accessing various services and schemes.

Ration Card

An official document issued by state governments that enables eligible households to obtain subsidized food grains and essential commodities under the Public Distribution System (PDS).

Nautapa and Extended Mahatapa

'Nautapa' refers to the nine hottest days of the year, occurring from the end of May to the first week of June. During this period, residents of Chhattisgarh experience intense heat. Through generational experience protective practices that regulate work and movement outdoors and consumption of food and drink have guided preventive behaviours in this period of extreme summer temperatures. In recent years, however, residents have observed shifts in weather patterns, with heat waves extending beyond the traditional 'Nautapa' period. This prolonged spell of extreme heat beyond nine days is locally referred to as 'Extended Mahatapa'

Abbreviations

ANM	Auxiliary Nurse Midwife
ASHA	Accredited Social Health Activist
AWW	Anganwadi Workers
CHC	Community Health Centres
CIMS	Chhattisgarh Institute of Medical Sciences
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EWS	Economically Weaker Sections
JSY	Janani Suraksha Yojana
LIG	Low Income Group
MGNREGA	Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act
MIG	Middle Income Group
MoHFW	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare
NUHM	National Urban Health Mission
PHC	Primary Health Centre
PIL	Public Interest Litigation
PMAY	Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana
PMMVY	Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana
SC	Sub Centre
UAN	Universal Account Number
UPHC	Urban Primary Health Centres

Executive Summary

The qualitative socio-cultural study in the Heat in Pregnancy project examines the gendered impact of extreme heat on marginalized urban populations in Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh. The focus of the study is pregnant women from poor communities, most of who live in informal settlements in the city. Insights from round table with academicians, civil society members, front line health workers, community representatives, legal practitioners and researchers, highlighted how climate change, urban displacement, informal employment, and infrastructural deficits intersect to intensify heat exposures, health, economic and social vulnerabilities.

Findings reveal that many poor households in urban Bilaspur have been displaced from their homes in rural or tribal areas due to development-induced factors and subsequently resettled in peripheral government housing colonies with inadequate access to basic services such as water, electricity, sanitation, healthcare, and cooling infrastructure. The infrastructural deficits limit residents' capacities to cope with extreme heat significantly. Women especially pregnant women face disproportionate exposure due to a combination of unpaid work, physically demanding paid labour, long working hours and limited opportunity for rest, hydration, and cooling. Hourly wage structures compel women to work through extreme heat often without breaks, increasing risk of dehydration, heat exhaustion, and adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes.

The discussion identified critical gaps in access to health and nutrition services. Newly developed resettlement colonies often lack accessible Anganwadi centres, compelling women to travel long distances to register for schemes and leaving them excluded from routine nutritional and health services. Cultural norms, fear of stigma, and widespread nutritional deficiencies contribute to delayed pregnancy disclosure and late engagement with antenatal care, resulting in missed opportunities for early detection of complications. Although public health and social protection schemes such as e-shram cards, Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY), and Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) exist, their implementation remains fragmented and exclusionary due to bureaucratic complexities, documentation barriers, corruption, and inadequate institutional support.

Working conditions further exacerbated women's vulnerabilities during pregnancy. Women employed in

informal and semiformal sectors like construction, retail, domestic work, street vending, and industrial units are routinely exposed to extreme heat without access to toilets, drinking water or spaces for rest. Protective labour regulations are poorly enforced, and mechanisms to address harassment and exploitation are largely absent.

Overall, the round table highlighted that extreme heat in Bilaspur functions as a multiplier of existing gender, class, and infrastructural inequalities. Despite multiple welfare schemes aimed at reducing vulnerabilities, weak implementation and lack of climate-responsive planning significantly undermine their effectiveness. The findings underscore the urgent need for integrated, gender-responsive, and heat-resilient urban policies that prioritize access to cooling, electricity, water, sanitation, healthcare, nutrition, and safe working conditions. Without systemic reforms and strengthening accountability, extreme heat will continue to deepen health risks, economic precarity, and social exclusion among the urban poor in Bilaspur.

Section 1:

INTRODUCTION

Extreme heat has emerged as one of the most pressing and yet under-recognized climate related risks in India, with profound implications for public health, livelihoods, and social equity. Rapid urbanization, climate change, and unplanned development have intensified heat exposure in cities, particularly affecting populations that are already socially and economically marginalized. The urban poor experience disproportionate vulnerabilities due to precarious housing, informal employment, limited access to resources and exclusion from the institutional support system. In this context, extreme heat operates not merely as an environmental stressor amplifying existing structural inequalities, but as a catalyst that compounds the everyday hardships of marginalised communities.

Bilaspur, a rapidly growing city in Chhattisgarh, provides a critical site for examining the dynamics.

Its convergence of rapid urbanization, severe heat stress, and entrenched social inequities offers a revealing context to understand how extreme heat intersects with urban poverty, gendered vulnerabilities, and access to public services. The city experiences prolonged and increasingly intense summer temperatures often exceeding 44-45 degrees Celsius, creating significant risks for those with limited adaptive capacity. Populations living in informal settlements face heightened vulnerability due to inadequate infrastructure and limited economic resources, making them disproportionately vulnerable to the dangerous impacts of extreme heat.

The Heat in Pregnancy India (HiP-I) project is a multidisciplinary study representing a critical intersection of climate science, clinical and socio-cultural maternal health research on the impact of extreme heat on birth outcomes and local adaptation strategies to mitigate extreme heat. The project funded by the Wellcome Trust and implemented by a consortium of academic and clinical partners, is being carried out in selected cities across three states: Haryana, Chhattisgarh, and Puducherry through a mixed-methods design. The report draws on findings of the round table conducted as part of the qualitative work package exploring barriers and enablers to heat adaptation among women from marginalized backgrounds in Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh.

This report is organised into seven interconnected sections. Section 2 situates Bilaspur's urban poor within the city and the diverse forms of precarity shaping their

livelihood struggles. Section 3 explores the institutional support provided by the government and the multiple challenges faced by communities in accessing these entitlements. Section 4 highlights the gendered realities of women's lives and provides a detailed account of the specific vulnerabilities experienced by pregnant women in Bilaspur. Section 5 sums up the gendered determinants of heat and health vulnerabilities faced by the urban poor women in Bilaspur. Section 6 identifies the barriers and proposes leveraging opportunities presented by collectives and government platforms to strengthen heat-health resilience. Finally, Section 7 synthesises the recommendations offered by round table participants, outlining opportunities for systemic action and community-centred strategies to address extreme heat in Bilaspur.

Section 2:

LOCATING THE POOR IN BILASPUR CITY

Typology of Urban Poor in Bilaspur

The examination of the composition of the urban poor in Bilaspur revealed a complex landscape of displacement and economic precarity. Dr. Satyabhama Awasthi, founder of the Vasudha Mahila Manch, a veteran activist with over three decades of experience, and a resident of Bilaspur identified three demographic groups of urban poor residing in Bilaspur city. The residents of a) informal settlements located along the railway tracks, b) the inhabitants of economically disadvantaged neighbourhoods like Kalu Mohalla predominantly engaged in domestic work, and c) the families residing in government resettlement housing like Deendayal Awas and Atal Bihari Awas colonies.

Citing findings of a survey conducted by the NGO, Nav Rachna, across seven districts of Chhattisgarh, Dr. Devjit Nandi described rickshaw pulling as being taken up predominantly by those belonging to displaced rural and tribal communities. There was a consensus among the Round Table participants that majority of the urban poor in Bilaspur consisted of displaced populations compelled to migrate individually or with families, to the city following the forcible acquisition of their lands for dams, industrial projects, or mining activities. Equipped with skills more suitable for rural living, they re-start their lives at the lowest rung of the social ladder in cities living in informal housing, earning their living from low paying, unprotected manual work. The most vulnerable poor among the migrants settle in informal settlements, jhuggi-bastis, or on encroached lands. Moving to the city comes with few guarantees of stability for the poor as informal settlements are subjected to eviction yet again because of city beautification drives. They might also face repeated displacement when the lands they stay on are taken over for developmental purposes without adequate notice. The most vulnerable among the urban poor have in the past been relocated to government housing colonies with meagre facilities. Those with some more means tend to settle down in formal slum areas across various neighbourhoods of Bilaspur city, occupying a comparatively more secure, though still precarious position within the urban poverty landscape.

Migration for such individuals and families represents a drastic form of adaptation, which rarely translates into improved wellbeing. Repeated cycles of displacement

coupled with inadequate institutional support and the erosion of familiar social networks and cultural resources, further intensify the socio-economic marginalisation of the urban poor. Climate change impacts, thus compound the vulnerability produced by the existing limited claim on resources and the inequalities that poor migrants experience in destinations of migration like Bilaspur.

Key message

Exhaustion due to extreme heat exposures affect capacities for productive work, reducing incomes and compounding existing socio-economic vulnerability.

Negotiating Survival and Livelihood in Bilaspur

The poor in Bilaspur city are often employed in the informal sector as daily wage workers. They work in the construction and manufacturing industries, as domestic workers or earn their living through petty self-employment as rickshaw pullers, hawkers and street vendors. Employment in the private sector is contractual and those engaged in manual work, are paid on a monthly, daily, hourly or on a piece-rate basis (compensation based on number of items produced). Re-building their lives in the city on low-paying work necessitates working long hours without breaks to maximize incomes. Women irrespective of their health and pregnancy status might have little choice but to work for prolonged periods without adequate rest, their bodies suffering severe physical duress. In conditions of high heat, the physiological strain experienced due to work worsens, and could result in dehydration, heat exhaustion and chronic fatigue given that access to drinking water, cooling appliances or rest is questionable. The urban heat island effect further impacts their rest and sleep at night, adversely affecting vitality, overall health and hence productivity. Extreme heat and exhaustion could also reduce incomes earned by the poor by shortening hours of work, causing ill health affecting capacities for work and reducing earning capacities.

Upon relocation, individuals experience intense hardships due to lack of social networks and institutional support. Moreover, in the city they are forced to spend on essentials like fruits, vegetables, water, fuel, etc. which were otherwise available at little or no monetary cost in their village. Urban poverty deepens the vulnerability

of the poor in the city by imposing additional financial burdens and health inequities. Dr. Yogesh Jain, the organizer and moderator of the round table, whose work on health and medical care in rural Bilaspur spans over two decades, reflected, “being poor in a village is very hard, but now I feel being poor in the city is even tougher”. Thus, the intersections of poverty, displacement, informal employment, living conditions, and heat stress deepen the economic precarity and vulnerability to illness among urban poor in Bilaspur.

The socio-economic constraints and attendant vulnerabilities restrict opportunities for heat adaptation among the urban poor and as a result, undermine their overall health and wellbeing.

Limited access to formal employment benefits means many are unlikely to receive sick leave or income protection. They often have lower levels of savings, poorer access to credit, and greater barriers to obtaining timely medical care. Together, the constraints intensify their inability to cope with extreme heat and recover from its impacts, ultimately jeopardizing future growth and prospects of social and economic mobility.

Section 3:

INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT: GOVERNMENT SCHEMES AND POLICIES FOR URBAN POOR IN BILASPUR

Given the severe vulnerabilities faced by the urban poor, the salience of social welfare schemes implemented by the government to alleviate poverty and improve living conditions of the urban poor in Bilaspur cannot be undermined. Participants in the discussion dwelt upon the scope, relevance and implementation of policies and programs designed specifically for the urban poor in the context of extreme heat.

They listed various government schemes that offered support in the areas of housing, electricity, water, and employment benefits. Although the schemes are not specifically focused on reducing extreme heat, they have implications for reducing heat exposures and their impacts.

Key message

The quality of publicly funded subsidized housing offered to the poor does not only fail to offer dignified shelter but also turns the dwelling units into 'heat traps.'

Housing: Survival Space for the Urban Poor

The Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY) is the leading scheme to provide housing facilities for the urban poor in Bilaspur. A central government scheme, the PMAY is aimed at providing 'Housing for All' including the Economically Weaker Sections (EWS), Low-Income (LIG), and Middle-Income (MIG) groups offering subsidies or financial assistance to eligible beneficiaries. The scheme fundamentally targets two kinds of households, first those residing in kaccha houses with land ownership receive financial assistance to build pukka houses, and second those without a home ownership receive subsidies to buy homes.

The Chhattisgarh state government additionally offers a housing scheme called the Atal Awas Yojana, a state-sponsored housing construction programme run by the Chhattisgarh Housing Board. The Atal Awas Scheme predominantly focuses on providing houses for those living in informal slums or encroachment areas, many of which are demolished for city beautification or infrastructure development. The dwelling units are relocated to resettlement colonies or government

housing under the Atal Awas Yojana.

Resettlement colonies constructed by the Chhattisgarh Housing Board are in peripheral areas of Bilaspur city, including Kalu Mohalla, Chingrajpara, Chathiti, Mini Basti, and Imlibhata. Situated on the outskirts of the city and at times beyond municipal limits, the colonies are effectively outside the jurisdiction and administrative responsibility of the municipality, leaving residents without adequate institutional support.

Under the central and state schemes, a person is eligible for housing only if they own land or reside on encroached land subsequently acquired for urban development. Individuals without legal landownership are excluded from accessing benefits of the central or state government scheme rendering this section of the population further vulnerable, reinforcing existing inequalities.

Housing offered by the state government in resettlement colonies built under Atal Awas Yojana according to Ms. Santoshi Verma from Mitwa Mahila Kalyan Seva Samiti consists of units in multistorey buildings with four to five floors but without a lift. Very basic in its structure, each unit has a small hall, a small bedroom, a kitchen, and a toilet. Prof. Pratibha Mishra, from the Department of Social Work, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya described the houses as unfit to live in, with several of them lacking even a front door, raising concerns about security and privacy. Overall, the construction quality leaves much to be desired with several houses having serious issues like wastewater leakage from the toilets into the houses on the floors below. Once allotted, government authorities assume no responsibility for maintenance of the housing units, and grievance redressal mechanisms are inaccessible.

Mr. Prafull Chandel, from Jan Swasthya Sahyog said government housing in the Mini Basti area offered little space. Entire families of 5-6 individuals are packed in small single-room units of four-by-six feet or eight-by-eight feet, serving as hall, kitchen, and bedroom simultaneously. The roofs are constructed with poor-quality tiles necessitating reinforcement with plastic sheets for protection from rain and sun. A combination of substandard construction materials plus severely cramped living spaces fails to reduce ambient temperatures indoors during hotter periods during summer. Thus, the high indoor temperatures in

government housing for the poor in Bilaspur heighten health risks, reinforcing existing vulnerabilities of the urban poor. Many of the resident poor are forced to buy desert coolers to cool the dwelling units. The expenditure adds to the economic burdens and to the labour of women whose responsibility it is to fetch water from the public taps.

Subsidized housing offered by the government thus offers little protection from the elements, with rising temperatures, poor construction materials, inadequate ventilation, and lack of shade turning them into heat traps. Their living conditions compel already vulnerable residents to rely on mechanical cooling devices, increasing their financial strain and deepening existing precarity.

Key message

Energy generation from National Thermal Power Corporation in Bilaspur contributes to rising temperatures in the city. However, the power surplus does not translate into regular and sufficient supply for the urban poor in the city.

i. Electricity Access: Systemic Failure in providing a Basic Necessity

The difficult conditions of survival for the poor are further heightened by the lack of facilities like electricity and water supply to the Atal Awas colonies. According to Mr. Chandel, the lack of formal electricity connections forces several households to tap electricity through informal methods. Multiple households tap electricity from a single line resulting in loose wires that are known to have caused incidents of electrocution in the area. The excessive demand for electricity and resultant load on the lines in summer lead to multiple power failures.

For most households, legal access to electricity remains unattainable due to the absence of the requisite documentation. The bureaucratic procedures required to obtain the documents are time-consuming and would mean foregoing work and wages for the day. This challenge is only compounded by the non-allotment of numbers to the dwelling units, making it impossible for the residents to acquire a valid address. The lack of institutional support and their peripheral location make the process of securing legal documentation for houses in these settlements a difficult and prolonged process. Thus, the governmental failure to ensure access to basic services for the urban poor in Bilaspur exacerbates the latter's social and economic vulnerabilities

translating into heat exposures or compounding them. Most participants in the round table were also of the opinion that the setting up of the National Thermal Power Corporation's plant (generating and distributing electricity across the country) makes Bilaspur a power surplus city but also contributes to rising temperatures in neighbourhoods in the plant's vicinity. However, it is ironic that its capacities of power production do not translate into electricity access for the most vulnerable of its residents.

Indoor temperatures rise significantly due to a combination of extreme outdoor temperatures, low thermal resistance of buildings, and the heat generated during daytime cooking. Frequent power cuts then disrupt nighttime rest, creating a continuous cycle of heat exposure. The persistence of indoor heat with high outdoor temperatures offers little respite to women engaged in both paid employment and unpaid domestic work; placing a substantial physical and mental health burden on them.

ii. Urban Water Supply and Systemic Exclusion

Water constitutes another basic resource to mitigate the adverse effects of extreme heat. According to Ms. Verma, residents in Awas colonies are not provided with individual piped water connections relying instead on a single shared community tap allocated to approximately twenty-four households. The community taps, however, do not receive regular and reliable water supply. Water is made available only during designated periods, typically for an hour each, in the morning and evening.

Women who are primarily responsible for water collection, are required to queue up at the shared taps to fetch water. They often make three to four trips, up and down the stairs, with buckets of water to make sure their family has enough. Climbing stairs with heavy loads during pregnancy and in high temperatures leads to significant physical strain. Their physical limitations mean that pregnant women must make twice as many trips to meet their household's daily needs for water, putting them under tremendous strain under conditions of extreme heat.

During summer, water shortages in Bilaspur can be particularly acute. The Awas colony typically does not get water supply for two to three consecutive days. Attempts to seek assistance from the municipal corporation are largely ineffective. Mr. Chandel also shared that the government's toll-free helpline number 110 intended to address such grievances is ineffective during water

shortages. The helpline number directs the complainant to their local ward members, who turn a blind eye claiming water shortages to be a common problem across Bilaspur for which no remedial measures are available.

At times, the local ward members resolve the issue by arranging water tankers, but they stay woefully inadequate due to poor supplies and unsuitable timings. The quantum of water arranged could be as low as two tankers for 100 households, with each household barely getting two buckets (60-80 litres) of water. The water is not distributed equally either, those living closer to the spot where the tanker parks, are able to corner a larger share leaving the rest with little water to meet their needs. It has also been observed that even when a second tanker is made available, it reaches the neighbourhood after everyone leaves for work, effectively excluding working populations.

Poor quality housing that traps heat, irregular electricity supply, and inadequate water availability mean cooling is a struggle for poor families and especially the women whose burdens increase due to the additional water they must fetch to meet the household's needs. The participants painted a picture of the vulnerability faced by the urban poor in Awas colonies, due to infrastructural neglect, bureaucratic indifference, and systemic exclusion from basic municipal services like housing, electricity, and water, all critical to cope with extreme heat. Coolers that could potentially offer relief from extreme heat to the urban poor in Bilaspur, are ineffective due to frequent disruptions in electricity and poor water supply. As a result, many poor households are compelled to operate coolers without water, significantly diminishing the appliance's cooling capacity.

Dr. Yogesh Jain emphasised that access to cooling devices should be recognised a basic human right in the context of extreme heat, noting that at temperatures reaching 44–45°C, few alternative measures are effective in reducing body heat. He further highlighted that pregnant women are particularly susceptible to heat stress due to the increased internal heat production associated with hormonal changes, compounded by foetal heat. The physiological factors heighten their vulnerability during extreme heat events increasing the risk of heat exhaustion, dehydration and other heat related illnesses. Therefore, pregnant women require additional protective measures, including reliable access to water, electricity, and other essential infrastructural arrangements, to effectively cope with extreme heat conditions. This must be considered a basic right and fundamental component of climate resilient urban planning.

iii. Employment Benefits and Bureaucratic Complexities for Urban Poor

The nature, duration, and intensity of physical work and opportunities available for rest determine the metabolic heat that is produced and experienced by the human body. Employment constitutes a critical priority for the urban poor and displaced populations arriving in Bilaspur in the hope of making a living. Ms. Verma highlighted the government's e-Shram cards scheme for employees in the informal sector, which acts as an identity for individuals in the unorganized sector. Each card holder receives a Universal Account Number (UAN) that facilitates access to job opportunities, a monthly pension of Rs. 3,000 per month after the age of sixty, and other benefits like skill development, social security, and welfare schemes.

Pregnant women with the e-Shram cards, are entitled to a direct bank transfer of a total of Rs. 30,000 in two instalments (Rs. 10,000 in the seventh month of pregnancy and Rs. 20,000 within three months after childbirth) to compensate for wage loss. Additionally, the card holder can avail financial assistance for institutional delivery under the Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) which offers Rs. 6,000 for the first childbirth and Rs. 6,000 for second girl child as a onetime instalment post childbirth, offering nutritional support and compensating wage loss. A mandatory prerequisite to avail the maternity benefits is possession of a valid e-shram card since the scheme is designed to compensate wage loss.

The scheme on paper and in practice offers a stark contrast. The e-shram cards are valid for a year and require yearly renewal for eligibility. The renewal process is both tedious and excruciatingly time-consuming process requiring multiple follow ups. The cards can be renewed online or at specific government authorized centres like Seva Kendras. Limited digital literacy among informal workers forces them to rely on the Seva Kendras, which operate only during government working hours that are unsuitable for working populations. Moreover, the renewal process requires extensive documentation for which they must run from pillar to post navigating various government departments.

Residents of resettlement colonies face additional challenges due to lack of identification documents like an Aadhar card or a Ration card since their housing units are not listed and have not been assigned a proper address. Without valid address proof, new applications, or those for renewal of e-shram cards are rejected. According to Ms. Verma, "Out of 100 daily wage workers, only around 12 manage to renew their cards and receive benefits". The

remaining majority, particularly, the most vulnerable, are unable to complete the renewal process, forced to choose between pursuing the process or going to work that is crucial for their daily survival. Given their marginality, they rarely have the networks, monetary resources, or the confidence to navigate bureaucratic complexities and corruption at government authorized centres. Potential beneficiaries are expected to make informal payments (as high as half the monetary benefit) to officials in the government centres to access the free services to which they are entitled. Though present, the patchy implementation of social protection schemes renders them largely ineffective in safeguarding livelihoods, alleviating socio-economic, and health-related vulnerabilities of the urban poor in Bilaspur.

Lack of employment protection, combined with income loss and reduced productivity during periods of extreme heat, further exacerbates poverty. Women are disproportionately affected because they shoulder a significant additional burden of unpaid labour, including fetching water, and caring for family members suffering from heat-related illnesses, while juggling pressures to hold on to their employment and minimise income losses. The overlapping pressures deepen existing gendered inequalities and heighten women's vulnerability during extreme heat events.

Key message

Protective measures, including reliable access to water, electricity, and other essential infrastructural arrangements key to shade and cooling, must be considered a basic right and fundamental component of climate resilient urban planning.

Section 4:

WOMEN'S HEALTH AND DISPROPORTIONATE IMPACT OF HEAT STRESS

i. Working Condition of Women in Urban Bilaspur:

Women from poor urban communities in Bilaspur live and work within the aforementioned larger context of limited access to basic services and social protection. According to the discussion, both men and women participate in paid employment that includes both formal and informal work. However, in many households, some men, despite being employed, refuse to contribute to household income compelling women to shoulder financial responsibilities along with the burdens of household work, even during pregnancy.

Women in formal employment work in government or private sectors. The larger proportion is employed contractually in the informal sector with little employment security. Those with low educational attainments (schooling up to primary level) engage in low paying but heavy manual work, domestic help, and work as daily wage labourers in construction, or loading and unloading goods. Women who have completed schooling are employed in service jobs in shops, malls, petrol pumps, restaurants, industries or as low level skilled workers.

Women working in malls and chain stores in Bilaspur face severe exploitation despite formal contractual employment. While the written agreement often stipulates eight-hour shifts, women are frequently required to work 12 hours or longer and remain at the workplace late into the night. They are compelled to perform strenuous tasks such as loading and unloading heavy goods, prohibited under Chapter IV of the Factories Act, 1948. Advocate Priti Rout, an independent legal practitioner, highlighted that women are often required to carry heavy loads, sometimes even during pregnancy, a clear violation of the law. Popular chain stores that have sprouted across the city often lack basic facilities like staff toilets and force employees to remain standing throughout their shift, thereby flouting the standards prescribed under the Factory Act, 1948. Pregnant women who cannot afford to give up on work, continue to work under the extremely difficult conditions due to the pressing need to earn income and support their families. Those who assert their basic rights or raise complaints stand to lose their jobs. The Vishaka Guidelines, intended to protect women from workplace sexual harassment, are rarely implemented, and those reporting harassment are either terminated or pressured to resign.

Women in Bilaspur also work in petrol pumps and as traffic guides where inadequate sanitation facilities pose a challenge. Prof. Mishra's study on women working as traffic guides reveals the lack of toilets as the key challenge they face as they labour outdoors. Domestic workers engaged in mopping, sweeping, and cooking, typically work in two shifts: morning to early afternoon (12pm-1pm) and late afternoon (3pm) to evening. According to Prof. Mishra, the recent unionization efforts among domestic workers have led to more standardized pay across domestic workers in Bilaspur. However, maternity protection and benefits remain non-existent as most women are unable to take leave during pregnancy or post-partum. Women work till the seventh or eighth month of pregnancy, and women in extreme financial difficulty continue to work until just days before delivery to maximize their earnings.

Conditions of heavy work are particularly dangerous during periods of extreme heat, as women are forced to travel and labour during the hottest hours of the day (early and late afternoon) resulting in severe fatigue and heat stress. Upon returning home, they are often unable to adequately cool their bodies or rest due to unreliable electricity and limited water supply. The structural deficiencies and systemic barriers to avail compensation for wages lost, create a vicious cycle exacerbating the vulnerabilities of pregnant women and limiting their capacity to cope with heat, while simultaneously increasing health risk associated with physically demanding work.

In the industrial areas of Bilaspur, such as Vyapar Vihar, women work in shops loading and unloading goods, housekeeping, and sorting products like turmeric, chilli, and jaggery. Many of the women are expected to perform physically demanding work outdoors under the scorching sun, regardless of their pregnancy status. Construction work is another major sector of informal employment for women. Sometimes, pregnant women are assigned less physically demanding tasks such as mixing cement and mortar. However, as construction advances, they are often required to undertake labour-intensive tasks like cleaning or moving materials. Since payments are made hourly, women rarely avoid strenuous work or working in high temperatures, despite the physical strain that can pose risks to their health.

According to Adv. Rout, women in these sectors often get a single short break of approximately five minutes for urination and hydration. While the Factory's Act, 1948, mandates access to drinking water and toilet facilities within six meters of each other, many factories or manufacturing units have a single water point in one corner and a toilet far away. The time a woman takes to visit the toilet, and drink water is counted as part of the break which is grossly insufficient. Pregnant women working in such factories are not given special considerations and expected to follow the same routine. The non-compliance with legal mandates compromises the health and well-being of workers, by increasing the risk of dehydration and heat-related health complications.

Ms. Sangeeta Sahu, an independent health researcher with extensive experience working across Chhattisgarh noted that women street vendors, rag pickers, sanitation workers are also particularly vulnerable to extreme heat. She emphasized that lack of safe public toilets deters the workers from using available facilities, further increasing their health risks. Concepts such as 'pink toilets' exist but such facilities are largely absent across Chhattisgarh. Ms. Sahu stressed the urgent need for safe public toilets for outdoor workers, particularly those inherently vulnerable to extreme heat due to the nature of their work.

ii. Abandonment of women and children

According to Adv. Rout, the abandonment of women and children belonging to poor settlements and Awas colonies is a widespread and persistent issue. Men either abandon their wives or enter second marriages. Abandonment typically occurs in two scenarios. In the first, men involved in extramarital relationships elope with their new partners, leaving behind their wife and children, forcing the women to rebuild their lives from the beginning. In this situation, although women may retain a place of residence, they face severe socioeconomic and emotional setbacks.

In the second scenario, women are subjected to domestic violence, coerced to leave their homes making them extremely vulnerable, often without access to basic amenities. Women sometimes pregnant are compelled to leave the household and care for their children in precarious and unsafe conditions. Deserted women with little economic means are often forced to encroach on public spaces due to their dire circumstances, residing in makeshift kuccha structures and undertaking menial labour such as rag picking to initially survive and provide for their children.

Men who take a second wife may continue residing in the same house with both partners, despite limited space and inadequate living conditions. According to Ms. Verma, many such men either refuse to work or fail to contribute to the household income, placing the entire financial responsibility on both wives for the care of their children. In most instances of abandonment, women remain unaware of the legal protections available to them or of services such as the One Stop Crisis Centre, which provides temporary shelter support for abandoned women and children. Even those who manage to approach a police station may be required to submit a written application, something many are unable to do due to low literacy levels and fear of bureaucratic procedures. Under these circumstances, women particularly pregnant women and those who were financially dependent on their husbands are compelled to prioritize rebuilding their lives while simultaneously caring for their children, leaving little scope to recognize or address the adverse impacts of extreme heat on their health and wellbeing. This struggle for basic survival also has serious implications for the labour and financial resources required for selfcare, antenatal needs, and postpartum recovery, further deepening their vulnerability.

Key message

Key message: The absence of Anganwadi centres in the resettlement neighbourhoods compromises the communities access to nutritional and ante-natal services.

iii. Pregnant Women's Health and Nutritional Services:

Anganwadi centres located within the neighbourhoods serve as a critical service delivery point for maternal and child health and nutrition. Ms. Verma noted that most Atal Awas colonies lacked an Anganwadi centre in their vicinity, as they were newly developed housing colonies. According to Ministry of Women and Child Development, an Anganwadi centre caters to 400-800 population in urban and rural areas, providing services like supplementary nutrition, immunization, pre-school education, health check-ups, nutritional education, and referral services for women and children. Supplementary nutrition targets all pre-schoolers, with special attention to severely malnourished children, pregnant and lactating women. In Chhattisgarh, pregnant and lactating women from poor communities receive ready-to-eat supplementary nutritional packet to fulfil the shortfall in meeting nutritional needs.

The absence of Anganwadi centres in the resettlement colonies compromises the access of resident communities to nutritional and ante-natal services crucial to maintaining the health of pregnant women and their unborn children. Women residing in these neighbourhoods are forced to travel 3-4 kms to access the nearest Anganwadi centre for registration. Registration enables access to cash benefits under the Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) offered by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW). This scheme offers a conditional cash transfer of Rs. 1,400 and Rs. 1,000 in rural and urban areas of Chhattisgarh respectively, to incentivize institutional delivery and reduce maternal and neonatal mortality. While the women manage to ensure registration at Anganwadi centres to access financial benefits, many are unable to avail nutritional services regularly due to the geographical distance involved. Consequently, the lack of proximate Anganwadi centres deprive women and children of comprehensive health and nutritional benefits they are entitled to.

In contrast, in more established urban slums of Bilaspur, the Anganwadi centre, Sub centres, Health and Wellness Centres and Primary Health Centres offer health and nutritional support to pregnant women. While the residents of Awas colonies are largely excluded from these benefits, Mr. Chandel further highlighted that even where Anganwadi centres exist, the quality-of-service delivery is often compromised. Although pregnant women register at the centres, routine health assessments like blood pressure, blood glucose testing, and health check-ups rarely occur due to lack of adequate infrastructure, equipment, and privacy within the centres.

Participants further described the overall situation of women, especially pregnant women, in the household and the community as particularly concerning. Gendered notions of women's roles within families and communities translate into neglect of their communities do not pay sufficient attention to women's nutritional needs. Women's food, nutrition, comfort and their arrangements for rest or sleep are often not prioritised within households. Malnutrition, poor ventilation, and health complications stemming from inadequate healthcare during extreme heat collectively impair thermoregulatory responses, reducing the body's ability to dissipate heat and endangering both pregnant women and their foetuses.

iv. Healthcare Services Access:

According to Ms. Naseem Shriwas from Samarpit, who works as a senior field worker with urban women in Bilaspur, women typically seek care from nearby sub-centres for minor ailments such as cough, cold, or general health concerns. If treatment is ineffective or symptoms worsen, they subsequently approach the District Hospital or Medical College Hospital which is the Chhattisgarh Institute of Medical Sciences (CIMS). For more serious health concerns, women may also seek care from local unqualified providers or private practitioners. Daily wage earners, in particular, prefer private doctors located close to their homes, to minimise expenses, time spent, and wages that could be lost. In areas such as Chuchiyapara, Ganesh Nagar, and Imlibhata, where PHCs and Sub-centres have existed for many years, women have established relationships with healthcare workers. Their familiarity with the personnel makes the facilities a preferred choice for minor health issues. Overall, women's first point of care is often the private sector or local practitioners, with government hospitals typically approached only when health conditions deteriorate.

Regarding pregnancy-related care, Mr. Chandel noted that women usually confirm pregnancy through private sector doctors, where blood tests and sonography may be prescribed. Following confirmation, they register their pregnancy at the local Anganwadi centre. Ms. Verma, who has conducted educational programs for pregnant women in urban slums, explained that once registered, antenatal care is provided by the Auxiliary Nurse Midwife (ANM), throughout pregnancy. During delivery, women with perceived risk or complication often prefer private facilities, choosing facilities where costs are comparatively lower. However most economically marginalized women ultimately seek care at the CIMS or District Hospital to avail government schemes.

Despite the provisions, Ms. Santoshi Vishwakarma, formerly a field worker with Jan Swasthya Sahyog and currently a nurse at the State Mental Hospital, Bilaspur, shared that many women delay pregnancy registration at Anganwadi centres during first trimester due to fear of miscarriages. This behaviour is shaped by the collective experience of foetal loss in early pregnancy due to heavy burdens of work coupled with severe nutritional deficiency and anaemia in Chhattisgarh. This widely shared experience is culturally interpreted as a result of 'evil eye'. Hence women and families tend to conceal pregnancies during the early months. Consequently, pregnancy is often disclosed only after the first trimester or once physical signs become visible.

Prof. Pratibha Mishra, corroborated these findings, noting that women in joint families often avoid disclosing pregnancy during the first three months resulting in delayed nutritional and medical care during early pregnancy, depriving the mother and child of essential nutrition during a crucial period of growth and development. Adv. Gayatri Suman emphasized, in communities where women's health and nutrition already receive limited care and attention, such delays can have adverse consequences for both maternal and foetal health. Ms. Vishwakarma further noted that postponing healthcare during early pregnancy delays early detection of easily treatable complications, paradoxically increasing the risk of miscarriage and reinforcing the cycle of fear and stigma.

Following the first trimester women often rely on traditional healers such as Baigas, or seek advice from elder women in the household, including mothers-in-law, grandmothers, or traditional birth attendants for antenatal care. Engagement with the formal health care systems frequently occurs only after four or five months of pregnancy. According to Prof. Mishra, tertiary facilities such as CIMS or District Hospital are typically considered a last resort.

Mr. Chandel added that many women residing in urban slums, are engaged in paid work until evening hours, making it difficult to access Anganwadi services during its operating hours. For working women,

Mitanins become the most accessible point of contact. Women often register pregnancies through Mitanins and reach out to them directly during delivery, bypassing other antenatal services. Despite the failure to seek antenatal care, Mitanins accompany women to public hospitals during delivery, partly due to the incentives. Women also prefer public hospitals to avail benefits under JSY scheme and to minimise expenses. In case of complications or high-risk cases, however, women frequently turn to nearby private nursing homes, despite high costs ranging from Rs. 25,000 to Rs. 30,000 due to perception of better quality.

This preference for private healthcare reflects a deep-rooted mistrust in the public health institutions. Mr. Ajay Anant from Guru Ghasidas Seva Sangh, an NGO that works with tribals and migrants, shared that those from poor urban communities often perceive treatment in public hospitals as risky, equating it to a "death sentence", highlighting widespread apprehension about government facilities. Participants also reported that women avoid visiting the District Hospital or Medical College Hospitals on Sunday, as admissions are often denied and patients are redirected to the private sector.

Such denial of services, inconvenient operating hours, lack of responsiveness, and difficulties navigating the public healthcare systems have collectively contributed to women's reluctance to seek healthcare from government facilities even during pregnancy, unless no alternative remains.

Section 5:

IN SUM: GENDERED DETERMINANTS OF HEAT-HEALTH VULNERABILITIES

This discussion on the gendered vulnerabilities of heat and health among urban poor women in Bilaspur illustrates how multiple, intersecting determinants and systemic failures shape their exposure to extreme heat. Migration driven by development-induced displacement depletes their existing assets. Additionally, limited skills unsuitable for urban economies, place them in informal, unregulated, low paying and insecure employment. Hence, not only are they exposed to harsh work conditions and subjected to prolonged working hours to make ends meet, but persistent poverty positions households at the margins, reducing their capacity to cope with rising temperatures.

The vulnerability of poor migrant women in cities intensifies with limited access to authorised social security and welfare benefits, inadequate postpartum wage support, lack of valid identification documents to claim entitlements, and weak enforcement of labour protections such as the Factory Act (1948) and Vishaka Guidelines.

Poor urban planning compounds heat risks through low quality housing, inadequate water and electricity supply, lack of safe toilets, and minimal cooling or green infrastructure.

Gaps in the health system, only compounded the existing heat-health challenges through insufficient antenatal, intrapartum, and postnatal care and limited awareness of heat-related maternal and child risks.

Gendered socio-cultural norms at the family and community level further burden and constrain women with caregiving responsibilities, financial dependence, unpaid labour, insufficient rest and inadequate food and nutrition. Delayed ANC care and distrust of public hospitals, leave them with fewer avenues for support in pregnancy.

The invisibility of women in realms of regional development, urban planning, poverty alleviation, and the poor planning and poor implementation of social welfare and health care services severely constrain the overall life circumstances and choices exercised for safety and health by poor pregnant women in Bilaspur. The unavailability of public goods, when refracted through the socio-cultural norms shaping their private sphere, further limit women's abilities to keep their bodies cool, have sufficient rest, undisturbed sleep and protect themselves from health impacts of excess physiological heat strain during pregnancy.

Section 6:

CAN BARRIERS BE HARNESSSED AS POINTS OF LEVERAGE TO ENABLE CHANGE?

While the systemic issues raised by the Round Table are crucial, could there be opportunities for strengthening government service provision and utilising existing community collectives to find solutions that support heat resilience among poor women in Chhattisgarh? Government schemes such as PMAY, Atal Awas, eShram, PMMVY, and JSY, though often perceived as limited in effectiveness, remain important and adaptable platforms that can be redesigned to better address overlapping vulnerabilities related to extreme heat, poverty, and maternal health. At the community level, unionised groups and informal collectives could play a key role in co-producing solutions, strengthening accountability, improving access to social protection, and fostering dialogue around gender-insensitive norms that affect maternal health outcomes.

At the systems level, existing policy flexibilities—such as adjustable UPHC working hours under NUHM—can be leveraged to align services with extreme heat conditions. Health infrastructure including Anganwadi centres, subcentres, and hospitals like CIMS provide a critical base for delivering heat-responsive services, while frontline workers (ASHAs, ANMs, Anganwadi Workers) act as trusted intermediaries. Strengthening their capacity through targeted training and support can enhance community resilience, reduce gendered vulnerabilities, and improve health outcomes among urban poor populations in Bilaspur.

Together, these interconnected enablers could offer practical opportunities to strengthen resilience, reduce gendered vulnerabilities, and improve health outcomes for urban poor communities in Bilaspur.

Key message

The roundtable recommends: infrastructural investment, societal engagement, and institutional support.

Section 7:

RECOMMENDATIONS

The roundtable recommends reshaping policy implementation through three interconnected pathways: infrastructural investment, societal engagement, and institutional support.

INFRASTRUCTURAL INVESTMENT:

i. Reassessment of State-Supported Housing Policies

Housing provided under state scheme in Atal Awas Colonies, requires urgent reconsideration. Extremely small living spaces for large families, coupled with poor construction quality, inadequate ventilation, and lack of basic amenities such as water and electricity, severely limit residents' ability to cope with extreme heat. It was recommended that housing policies be revisited by the state to ensure dignified, climate-resilient living conditions for poor and vulnerable populations who disproportionately bear the brunt of extreme heat despite contributing least to climate change. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) funds must be diverted towards infrastructure development and maintenance of poor urban settlements.

ii. Prevent Power and Water Cuts During Summer

Effective coordination with the electricity department is critical to ensure uninterrupted power supply during the summer months. While power outages are often attributed to pre-monsoon maintenance activities, sustained electricity availability is essential to support cooling infrastructure and mitigate heat-related risks, particularly for vulnerable populations such as the elderly, children, pregnant women, outdoor workers, and low-income households. Policies should prioritize minimizing planned outages during periods of extreme heat and ensuring contingency arrangements where disruptions are unavoidable. This is possible for a state that generates surplus electricity, where residents naturally expect reliable and continuous power supply, yet never fully benefit from it while bearing the brunt of excessive heat caused by the presence of the thermal power plant.

Similarly, summer water management policies must focus on preventing disruptions in water supply and ensuring equitable and adequate access to potable water. Special emphasis should be placed on safeguarding water availability for vulnerable communities through advance planning, efficient distribution mechanisms, and emergency provisioning during peak summer months.

iii. Access to Clean Toilets, Drinking Water, and Public Rest Spaces for Women

A major challenge faced by working women, irrespective of pregnancy status, is the lack of access to clean toilets and safe drinking water. Under the country-wide campaign Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Mission), and Smart City initiatives, the provision of clean gender-sensitive washroom facilities, hydration stations, and rest areas should be made a critical policy priority. Government bodies, NGOs, and philanthropic organizations must be mandated to implement these facilities. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) funding should be diverted towards construction and maintenance of such cooling stations.

The absence of such amenities, forces many women to restrict water intake to avoid urination during travel or work, leading to dehydration and other health complications. The establishment of rest rooms equipped with drinking water, functional fans or coolers, seating areas, and toilets at major intersections, marketplaces, traffic signals, and worksites, particularly for Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) workers was strongly recommended. Facilities should be accessible to all women, especially when pregnant or lactating. Special attention needs to be paid to women engaged in outdoor work enabling timely rest, hydration and relief. Access to facilities could improve women's health outcomes and should be approved through decentralised municipal-level governance.

The inclusion of such infrastructure in city development or master plans is critical. Workers' unions must be involved in determining the location of facilities to ensure accessibility and utilisation. Existing public toilets often remain unusable due to encroachment, lack of water, or poor maintenance, highlighting the criticality of maintenance and monitoring of infrastructure and service provision. Smart City planning must also account for displaced and migrant populations and their heightened vulnerability to extreme heat.

iv. Misting and Cooling Infrastructure in Public Spaces

The installation of misting systems and other cooling mechanisms at major public places was recommended. They should be prioritised in high-density areas where individuals especially outdoor workers and commuters are exposed to direct sunlight for prolonged periods.

SOCIETAL ENGAGEMENT:**i. Addressing Superstitions and Misinformation during Pregnancy**

Much of the knowledge women acquire during pregnancy is based on folk wisdom and advice from elders, shaped by collective experience. Some of the practices followed are scientifically inaccurate and can prove harmful. Beliefs related to the “evil eye” often discourage disclosure of pregnancy, delay early detection of complications, and impede timely medical treatment increasing the risk of adverse outcomes. Maternal health policies and programs must therefore prioritise awareness campaigns address customs and superstitions that can reinforce existing maternal health inequalities, with culturally sensitive yet evidence-based messaging.

ii. Public Awareness and Early Warning Systems on Heat Stress

Given that most people recognised rising temperatures as a concern but remain largely unaware of the specific ramifications for pregnancy and newborns, strengthening public awareness becomes essential. Public awareness initiatives on heat stress, including mobile-based alerts, hoardings, and billboards with specific messaging on impacts of extreme heat on health of general population and vulnerable population were recommended. Disaster management authorities should develop targeted early warning systems addressing the specific risks of extreme heat at different stages of pregnancy, childbirth and care for newborns. While heat has traditionally been normalised in India, and Chhattisgarh, the increasing intensity and duration locally described as “Extended Mahatapa” rather than the customary “Nautapa” must be communicated to emphasise the severity and threat of changing nature of heat. Enhancing such awareness will help address the currently nascent public discourse on heat-related maternal and infant health risks.

iii. Formation of a Pregnant Women Welfare Association

The establishment of a Pregnant Women’s Welfare Association was proposed to function as a community based independent monitoring and evaluation body. Such an association could assess working conditions, track policy implementation, and advocate for pregnant women’s rights and welfare, thereby strengthening accountability mechanisms. The associations can also collectively identify, support, and advocate for women during periods of abandonment. The association can strengthen women’s agency, improve access to

entitlements, and ensure early intervention through coordinated community-based monitoring.

INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT:**i. Strengthening Monitoring and Evaluation of Health Services**

Systematic and robust monitoring and evaluation of Anganwadi Workers (AWWs), Mitanins, Urban Primary Health Centres (UPHCs), Community Health Centres (CHCs), and other health facilities was recommended. Given Bilaspur’s significant migrant population, special attention must be paid to assessing the extent, quality, and utilisation of health services by migrant communities, particularly pregnant women who often lack formal documentation. Although monitoring mechanisms in the form of ANM supervision, ASHA/Mitanin registers, and other documentation and review processes exist within the health system, they remain fragmented and inadequate. Moreover, monitoring mechanisms also tend to exclude migrants and undocumented populations. Strengthening and formalising monitoring frameworks is therefore essential to ensure equitable service delivery and identify gaps affecting vulnerable populations. Additionally, the group reiterated that the working hours of Anganwadi Centres and UPHCs should be adjusted based on the convenience of the population within their respective catchment areas. Although such flexibility is already permitted under the National Urban Health Mission (NUHM), the functioning of facilities with revised timings should be properly monitored.

ii. Provision of Preventive and Climate-Responsive Health Services

It was proposed that PHC, and CHCs, be mandated to implement preventive heat-health services during summer months. This calls for investments in cooling infrastructure such as adequate ventilation systems, ceiling fans, drinking water coolers, and shaded waiting areas that provide immediate relief to heat-stressed pregnant women. Cooling interventions must be integrated with strengthened nutritional support programs, including regular distribution of supplementary nutrition, micronutrient supplementation, and nutrition education sessions tailored to pregnant women’s increased needs during heat exposure. Such comprehensive facility-level preparedness would ensure that the first point of healthcare contact actively mitigates rather than exacerbates heat-related maternal health risks.

Enhanced coordination between the Health Department and the Women and Child Development Department is necessary to provide enhanced nutritional support for pregnant women beyond ready-to-eat supplements. Community-based nutrition programs like mid-day meals should be explored, with climate-appropriate cooling and hydrating foods to help women and children cope with heat. Anganwadi centres and sub-centres should also function as safe resting spaces, equipped with toilets and drinking water, particularly during peak summer months for pregnant women.

iii. Capacity Building of Frontline Health Workers

Capacity building of frontline health workers including Mitans, AWWs, ANMs, and others must be institutionalised. Regular refresher training on heat prevention, protection, and mitigation strategies should be conducted prior to the summer season, with specific focus on vulnerable groups such as pregnant women.

iv. Heat-Sensitive Workplace Policies

Industries and organized workspaces should implement flexible working hours during summer months. Work shifts must be adjusted to avoid peak heat hours, with shaded resting areas and provisions for leave or workload modifications during extreme heat. Pregnant women, in particular, should receive adequate breaks, be exempted from physically strenuous work, and allowed to leave workplaces earlier to avoid peak heat exposure.

Advocacy and legal measures must be pursued to expedite enforcement of workplace protections for pregnant women. Constitutional provisions, such as Article 39(f), which mandates that women and children should not be compelled to work under conditions detrimental to their health, can serve as a legal foundation. Judicial intervention could translate the legal provisions into enforceable guidelines and enable punitive action against non-compliant organizations.

